

Climate-resilient strategy planning using the SWOT methodology: A case study of the Japanese wind energy sector

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ABSTRACT

As climate change leads to more frequent and intense extreme weather events, industry stakeholders and policymakers must assess their business strategies, practices, and entire sector policies under these uncertain conditions. Much recent research has integrated quantitative climate risk modeling into frameworks to engage policymakers and inform adaptation decisions in a general way, but relatively little attention has been devoted to extending this to strategic business and investment decisions. This falls short of identifying economic opportunities and threats in a wider socio-economic context, such as the development of new technologies or evolving political and regulatory environments. Here, a methodology is developed to integrate quantitative climate risk modeling with SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) which is commonly used in business and investment strategic planning. This moves the focus from avoidance of negative outcomes to prospective planning in an evolving environment. This methodology is illustrated with a case study of the Japanese wind energy sector, using open-access data and the open-source climate risk-assessment platform CLIMADA. This Climate risk assessment indicates threats from increasing damages to the wind energy infrastructure, as well as the profitability of typhoon-resistant wind turbines under present and future climate. Expert interviews and extensive literature research on opportunities and threats, however, also show that the transition towards renewable energies faces restrictive market dynamics, political and social hurdles, which set external conditions surpassing physically-informed dimensions. Beyond this illustrative case study, the methodology developed here bridges established concepts in climate risk modeling and strategic management and thus can be used to identify industry-centric ways forward for climate-resilient planning across a wide range of economic sectors.

1. Introduction

The warming climate and corresponding increase in intensity and frequency of extreme weather events (Seneviratne et al., 2021) are rapidly changing the conditions under which businesses and entire economic sectors must operate. Planning strategic investments under this climate uncertainty can be highly challenging. Extreme weather events may cause high losses, disrupt businesses, and lead to rapid changes in the socio-economic context (Mizuno, 2014; Ebi et al., 2021).

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Climate risk models are powerful tools that can help inform adaptation decisions, as they provide quantitative means to assess (economic) costs and benefits of adaptation measures in the form of averted losses under different climate pathways. The underlying logic of such models is usually based on the IPCC's concept of risk as the product of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability (Field et al., 2014). In order to become useful, the models need to be combined with complementary qualitative methodologies to engage stakeholders and flexibly take account of key aspects of the specific decision context. Thus far, such methodologies (e.g. stakeholder analysis and expert interviews) have been developed to embed quantitative climate risk modeling into processes to inform adaptation policy decisions at local to national levels (Souvignet et al., 2016). For many businesses and economic sectors, these methods may not traditionally lie within the scope of their knowledge and activities, thus they may fall short of identifying opportunities and threats in a wider socio-economic context, such as the development of new technologies or evolving political strategies favoring certain solutions over others. While some firms have integrated quantitative climate risk modeling into their business decisions (notably re-insurers), this remains limited to large firms specialized in risk assessments, and has not yet been widely taken up in strategic business planning.

To diminish the gap between climate risk knowledge and business-driven strategy planning, here we propose an innovative, generalized framework that integrates quantitative climate risk modeling into SWOT analyses (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats), which is a well-established concept in strategic management as already assessed by (Pesonen and Horn, 2014) (see Section 2). To demonstrate what is possible with openly available data and modeling tools, an illustrative case study is provided using only openly available data and using the open-source modeling platform CLIMADA (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Siguan et al., 2023) (see Section 3).

The framework is illustrated for typhoon-resilient strategic management, using the case of the wind energy sector in Japan in the context of climate change. Following the Fukushima nuclear disaster in 2011, the Japanese energy sector has been confronted with pivotal socio-economic challenges (Mizuno, 2014; Aditi et al., 2021; Vivoda, 2014). Wind energy has been seen as having the largest economic potential among all renewable energies (Mizuno, 2014), but is also heavily exposed to the risks of tropical cyclones (typhoons). This exposure may well increase in a changing climate (Knutson et al., 2020, see also Section 3). Climate-sensitive insights into *threats* and *weaknesses* faced by the Japanese wind energy sector are sought, and *strengths* and *opportunities* are being explored, through the use of open-access data, assorted literature, expert interviews, and the open-source risk modeling platform CLIMADA (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019). This paper emphasizes typhoon-resilient strategy planning rather than a comprehensive climate resilience assessment, demonstrating how to apply the framework to address a specific aspect of climate impacts. Thereby, the paper highlights the economic potential of renewable energy investments and assesses key challenges in overcoming market and regulatory barriers, making it applicable to a wide range of industries dealing with climate risks.

Overall, the elaborated framework and example show that tools and methods to include climate-resilient thinking into business strategies and policy-making may be readily at hand and that consideration must not only include the aversion of future damages but can incorporate the potential of new opportunities. This allows us to shift the discourse from avoidance of negative outcomes to strategic planning in an evolving environment.

The paper is divided into 4 sections. Following the introduction, Section 2 sets up the theoretical foundation for using the SWOT methodology and introduces how to adapt it to incorporate climate risk modeling. Section 3 applies the theoretical SWOT framework to the illustrative case study of Japan's wind energy sector. The discussion Section 3.3 interprets these results and addresses limitations of the study. Finally, Section 4 of the paper summarizes key findings and emphasizes the effectiveness of a climate-resilient SWOT methodology for analyzing economic sectors and improving strategic planning under climate risk.

2. Climate-resilient SWOT analysis

SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) has long been established as a framework to support strategic business and investment decisions (Eremit and Weber, 2016). It serves as a natural entry point for integrating climate risk modeling into decision-making processes. Within the scope of this article, it functions as an integrative approach for assessing the potential of business and investment opportunities (Namugenyi et al., 2019). SWOT can be flexibly conducted at varying scales and with diverse methodologies, encompassing expert opinion, workshop-oriented approaches, as well as quantitative analyses. As a strategic planning tool, it should focus on factors that accelerate, hinder or influence projects and goals (Culp et al., 2016). The framework is divided into an internal analysis focusing on the *strengths* and *weaknesses* of the firm or organizational unit, and an external analysis focusing on the *opportunities* and *threats* in the surrounding market, regulatory, and risk environment (Eremit and Weber, 2016). Strengths represent an organizational unit's internal competencies and positive assets (Culp et al., 2016; Burstein and Holsapple, 2008). Weaknesses are the organizational unit's constraints obstructing efficient performance. Opportunities are seen as assets facilitating the organizational unit to capitalize on its offerings (Culp et al., 2016). Threats incorporate factors delaying the organizational unit's reachable milestones (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015). Each of these aspects should be assessed relative to the specific business or investment decision at hand: that is, while a given firm may have many strengths in general, its strengths relative to a specific business decision should be the focus of assessment. While SWOT analysis was originally developed to focus on the business opportunities for a single firm, it has been adapted and applied to entire sectors, such as the potential for renewable energy to contribute a greater proportion of a nation's electricity supply (Chen et al., 2014; Gonzales and Poletti, 2021; Igliński et al., 2016).

Contributing to the needs of businesses for quicker and cost-efficient ways to strategically plan for the future uncertainty of climate change, (Pesonen and Horn, 2014) proposed and evaluated a method of representing product-related climate information in the form of a "Climate SWOT tool". This approach combines SWOT methodology with product life-cycle assessment, in order to

Fig. 1. Climate-resilient SWOT analysis: Incorporating strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats posed by current climate and climate change into strategic planning, along a well-known management tool focusing on internal and external analysis of factors.

include analysis of climate and environmental impacts throughout each stage of a product, from sourcing raw materials through eventual disposal and recycling.

This paper contributes to the promising body of research and practice by showing how SWOT can be further enhanced by incorporating quantitative climate impact modeling. Climate risk modeling can assess societal risks arising from diverse aspects of climate change, ranging from slow, gradual changes such as sea-level rise (Vousdoukas et al., 2018) and melting permafrost (Karjalainen et al., 2019) to increasing chances of extreme events (Donat et al., 2020) such as floods and typhoons. These can be combined with cost-benefit analyses that estimate the performance of different strategies under future scenarios of climate change (Bresch and Aznar-Siguan, 2021). These analyses can also help business leaders gain insights into potential 'black swans' (Taleb, 2007) – extreme events that are possible even in the present climate, but may by chance not have happened in a given location in recorded history (Sillmann et al., 2021). One could imagine business leaders in New Orleans conducting a SWOT analysis in 2004: if they had considered only recent local history, they would have failed to account for the possibility of an extreme event such as Hurricane Katrina that did occur in the following year. Climate risk modeling with probabilistic event sets (Kropf et al., 2022) offers one way to include such (recently) unprecedented extreme events in a risk analysis.

Fig. 1 shows our general approach to integrating climate risk modeling into climate-resilient SWOT analysis. Climate-related *strengths* and *weaknesses* focus on aspects of the system (a firm or sector), including previous climate-related damage and the potential of the system to adapt to climate change. Implications of these for the competitive advantage of the firm or sector are also crucial for strategic planning, as adaptation often entails up-front costs that deliver future benefits. *Opportunities* and *threats* include the traditional emphasis on political, regulatory, and societal conditions and their possible future development. Beyond this, the presented framework also considers evolving climate-related hazards, including extreme weather events and the effects of climate change. Assessment of each of the SWOT elements relies on multiple methodologies, including climate risk modeling alongside traditional qualitative methodologies such as expert interviews, workshops, and literature and market research. As shown in Fig. 1, methods for the internal analysis can be used to determine both strengths and weaknesses depending on the results of the analysis. An assessment of climate-related damage could for example indicate a strength if the analysis showed a substantial decrease in damage due to an available adaptation measure or a weakness if it showed large damage. Similarly, methods for the external analysis can determine both opportunities and threats depending on the results. Experts for example may point towards opportunities such as financial support systems, or the literature may reveal threats such as regulatory hurdles.

3. Illustrative case study: Typhoon-resilient SWOT analysis for the wind energy sector in Japan under climate change

As mentioned in the study of Sun et al. (2023), the electric power sector is crucial for an economy and climate change response. It must therefore effectively manage climate risks and enhance adaptability for stable operation (Sun et al., 2023). Here, we illustrate an application of the climate-resilient SWOT framework, using the case of the wind energy sector in Japan. The wind energy sector in Japan has seen a pivotal change in the socio-political context in the aftermath of the Fukushima nuclear accident in 2011 (Esteban and Portugal-Pereira, 2014). While the sector has been rapidly growing as a lower-risk alternative (Esteban and Portugal-Pereira, 2014) to nuclear power, it may be threatened by the projected increase of risk from the higher intensity of typhoons (Walsh et al.,

2019). Typhoons are intense low-pressure systems that form over warm ocean waters which can produce strong winds, heavy rainfall, and typhoon surges (Nayak and Takemi, 2020). As a result of climate change, typhoons are expected to diminish in frequency but amplify in intensity (Walsh et al., 2019). In particular, these strong winds can be a challenge for wind turbines. During a typhoon, typical turbines must be stopped to avoid structural damage which may lead to increasing periods of production losses (Chen et al., 2009). Extremely intense winds can furthermore lead to structural damages and even the complete loss of turbines (Chou et al., 2019). At the same time, more typhoon-resistant turbines are currently being developed (Rechsteiner, 2023), some even capable of producing energy during typhoons (Challenge Energy Inc., 2020; General Electric, 2018). This, together with Japan's increasing exposure to typhoons (Nayak and Takemi, 2020) and the above-mentioned development of its wind energy sector, makes Japan an interesting country to examine. The development of Japan's wind sector presents strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

For the illustrative climate-resilient SWOT analysis, focusing on typhoons, we consider the potential to expand wind-power production capacity in Japan, in order to meet societal goals of reduced reliance on nuclear power and fossil fuels. We consider a hypothetical development and investment decision: expanding wind-power production capacity using either conventional or typhoon-resistant wind turbines. We analyze the performance of these in present and future climate. While climate impact modeling and cost-benefit analysis are key components of the analysis, we combine these with other sources of evidence to build a more comprehensive understanding of enabling and hindering factors.

3.1. Methods

3.1.1. Literature research

Relying on literature research, energy market components were explored concerning Japan's infrastructure and stakeholders, their positions, and interests. Literature was searched on Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar where references were sought with the help of keywords, such as *wind energy*, *Japanese energy sector*, *energy market*, *typhoons*, *wind turbines*, and *renewable energies*. Different types of documents were selected, with peer-reviewed articles and reports forming the majority. The relevance and further use of literature for the project were determined while reading its abstract and conclusion and considering its topicality. We also consulted sources cited within this selected literature, for a total of 163 sources of information, including scientific papers and websites (a full list is given on request). We then sorted and synthesized these sources based on the four SWOT components. Thus, it was possible to provide an overview and include findings from the literature that embed the results of the quantitative analysis of this paper in a broader context.

3.1.2. Expert interviews

Following literature research, remaining gaps, contradictions, or ambiguities were explored through expert interviews with two professors at ETH Zurich who are active in the field of renewable energies, specifically wind energy, with experience on national and international levels. The interviews were semi-structured, *i.e.* the interview questions and topics were intentionally prepared, but room was left for follow-up questions and spontaneous restructuring of the interview in order to benefit as much as possible from the knowledge of the respective interview partner (Adams, 2015). The questions were phrased in such a way corresponding to the SWOT components. They were selected to fill the gaps that remained from the literature review and discrepancies observed in the research were addressed. The interviews were both held in an online meeting via Zoom. While a simple transcription was created directly for the first interview, for the second interview, a simple transcription was created afterwards based on a recording. Thus, the interviews were not only a further source of knowledge, but also a reference point for which aspects should be dealt with in greater depth in the paper. At the same time, they were an inspiration for further research and future work.

3.1.3. Climate impact assessment

Modeling approach. The climate impact assessment analyses potential wind damage and wind-energy production in present and future climates, with a hypothetical expansion of wind-energy production using either conventional or typhoon-resistant wind turbines. We use the open-source risk assessment tool CLIMADA, an open-source global probabilistic risk modeling platform (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Bresch and Aznar-Siguan, 2021). It provides a modeling framework for users to combine hazard (a probabilistic map of event intensities), exposure (a map of values that are exposed to a hazard), and vulnerability (impact functions that determine the degree of effect from a certain hazard on an exposure) to calculate risk. From a given hazard, exposure, and vulnerability an impact can be calculated. One can combine the probabilistic impact data from event sets to risk metrics, and investigate how climate change affects these risks and how adaptation measures can change the risk.

Wind turbines. We identified current wind turbine locations by using a query to filter data available on the crowd-sourced mapping platform OpenStreetMap (OSM) and an interface to this for CLIMADA (Mühlhofer et al., 2023, 2024). Limiting the data to locations that are energy "generators" or "plants" and produce energy with "wind" resulted in 2102 individual point locations representing wind turbines in Japan (see Fig. 2). To simplify this illustrative analysis, only onshore turbines were included, because of the differing characteristics of on- and offshore turbines.

For the hypothetical development and investment decision in this illustrative case study, we assume that one additional wind turbine would be built close to each of the existing wind turbine locations, doubling the total number of onshore wind turbines in Japan. We then assess the performance of these new turbines, comparing this for conventional or typhoon-resistant turbine designs. We make the simplifying assumption that each new conventional turbine would have the capacity equal to the average of the Eurus Energy's wind farms in Japan of 1.82 MW (Eurus Energy Holding Corporation, 2023), and that each new typhoon-resistant wind

Table 1Characteristics of the considered two wind turbines types *conventional* and *typhoon-resistant*.

Turbine type	Capacity (MW)	Asset Value (Mio US\$)	Yearly costs (Mio US\$)
Conventional	1.82	2.37	0.073
Typhoon-resistant	4.10	5.33	0.166

turbine would have a capacity of 4.1 MW corresponding to the average of Vestas' typhoon-resistant model (Vestas, 2022). To each turbine the price of the turbine type is assigned as value, which was assumed to be 1.3 Mio US\$/MWh according to Blewett (2023). For conventional turbines this is an asset value of US\$2 366 000, and for the typhoon-resistant turbines US\$5 330 000. The values are summarized in Table 1. While this is a stylized example, each of these modeling assumptions could well be modified to allow for analysis of any other scenario of wind-production expansion that investors, entrepreneurs, or officials may wish to consider.

Typhoon wind damage. We examine the current average damage and future risk of damage to wind turbines caused by typhoons. We use synthetic tropical cyclone (TC) event sets generated from the STORM model (Bloemendaal et al., 2020), a statistical model based on the historical records from the IBTrACS (International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship) archive from 1980 - 2017 (Knapp et al., 2010). We use the baseline climate (1980–2017) and future climate (2015–2050) event sets from Bloemendaal et al. (2020, 2022). For the future climate TC event set, the STORM C dataset is made using the SSP585 high emissions scenario, derived for four different climate models. We here report median impact values over the four models. Bloemendaal et al. (2022) note that different emissions scenarios do not result in substantially different TC hazard sets before 2050, though users could use these models to generate further TC event sets for alternate emissions scenarios. With these TC event sets, we generate a single intensity map per typhoon track consisting of the maximum 10- minute sustained wind speed at 2 meters above ground for the whole typhoon duration (both for current and future climate). The wind fields are computed from the tracks using the (Holland, 2008) model at a resolution of 30 arc-seconds (see Fig. 2) and are converted from 1 to 10 min sustained winds using the conversion factor 0.88 as implemented in the risk platform CLIMADA (Siguan et al., 2023). Both the baseline and future climate TC sets consist of 10 000 years of generated TCs. Each track is interpolated to a temporal resolution of 30 min before computing the maximum wind fields.

Impact calculation. We define impact (damage) functions for each wind turbine type, specifying the percentage of asset value lost at a given wind intensity. These damages represent repair costs for weak winds up to total losses at very high intensities. For conventional turbines we fitted the impact function based on the probability of buckling of non-yawing turbines from (Rose et al., 2013). For additional information on the impact damage functions consult Appendix B. The resulting function estimates no impact up until wind speeds of around 55 m/s (based on with-stand speed information from General Electric (2018)), reaching up to 100% damage to the conventional turbines at wind-speeds around 90 m/s (see Fig. 3). For typhoon-resistant turbines, we assumed the same sigmoid functional form as for the conventional turbines based on the work of Rose et al. (2013), but shifting the curve by +15 m/s to represent higher typhoon resistance, matching the withstand speeds found in the literature (General Electric, 2018) (see Fig. 3).

CLIMADA is then used to compute annual average damages from typhoons for the historic and future climates (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Siguan et al., 2023). This is done by a spatial overlay of hazard and exposure while factoring in the impact function. The impact I_{ij} for a specific location j for event i is given by

$$I_{ij} = E_j f(h_{ij}), \quad (1)$$

where E_j is the exposure value for location j , f the impact function and h_{ij} the hazard intensity at location j for the event i . For this study, the interest lies in the annual average impact defined as

$$AAI = \sum_j \sum_i I_{ij} v_i, \quad (2)$$

where $v_i = 1/10000$ is the annual occurrence probability of event i , and I_{ij} the impact at location as define in Eq. (1).

3.1.4. Natural hazard and climate risk assessment: Wind energy production

The CLIMADA framework is suitable to model both negative (damages to turbines) as well as positive (production of turbines) effects of natural hazards. Thus, the CLIMADA framework was also used to determine the total wind energy that can be produced in Japan by the current infrastructure during typhoons, as well as during normal wind conditions.

For the exposures, the value of wind turbines was changed from the asset value to the maximal production capacity (cf. Table 1) for either type of turbine.

For the energy production under normal conditions, a single annual average wind map (100 m above sea level) from the global wind atlas was used as hazard map to estimate production over a year (Davis et al., 2023). Estimates of average wind maps for future climates are not readily available from the global wind atlas. While not considered in this illustrative study, these could be extracted from global climate model runs as available for instance from the Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) project (Eyring et al., 2016; Haarsma et al., 2016). For energy production during typhoons, we use the STORM C event sets as described above for baseline and future climate. We computed these on an hourly resolution, defined as maximum 10-minute sustained wind per hour per event. These are then used to obtain average annual productions from typhoons (cf. Eq. (2)). This approximation leads to an overestimation of the produced energy before reaching the cut-off, but also overestimates the time when the cut-off is exceeded.

Fig. 2. Visualization of hazard (left, tropical cyclone wind field) and exposure (right, wind turbine locations) data.

Fig. 3. The impact functions of the wind turbine types used to calculate the fraction of damage done to the total value of the corresponding wind turbine at given wind-speeds.

Both mechanisms lead to opposite changes in energy production. In the context of this illustrative case study, we did not further elaborate on quantifying these effects.

Instead of damages, the impact functions now represent energy production. These production functions give the percentage of the total turbine capacity in watts per hour (value of the exposure layer) in function of the wind-speed, *i.e.*, they are power curves (see Fig. 4). We assume that the turbine begins to produce energy (cut-in speed) at 3 m/s, and that maximum power is reached 15 m/s for both turbine types were assumed according to literature (Carrillo et al., 2013; Clifton et al., 2013; Bauer and Matsysik, 2023; Jeon et al., 2015). The speed at which the turbine must be stopped to prevent damage (cut-out speed) was assumed to be 25 m/s for typhoon-resistant turbines and 22 m/s for the conventional turbines, following Vestas (2022).

3.1.5. Cost-benefit analysis (synthesis)

A cost-benefit analysis was conducted where the benefits were calculated by multiplying the produced energy during typhoons and normal wind conditions with 210 US\$/MWh, which is the assumed average electricity price of household and industry in Japan according to IEA (2021a), Global Petroleum Prices (GPP) (2023). The costs were assumed to only be composed of the investment costs (cost of the turbine equal to the total value of the asset, cf. Table 1), the yearly running costs (US\$154 826 994 for status-quo, US\$348 845 583 for typhoon-resistant according to Steffen et al. (2020), Morthorst et al. (2008)), and costs from damage to the wind turbines. An exploitation time of 20 years was considered. The Net-Present-Value (NPV) and Benefit-Cost-Ratios (BCR) were calculated with a discount rate of 5%, which represents a common interest rate (Attema et al., 2018). However, discount rates can vary widely depending upon context, *e.g.*, the “2022 Cost of Wind Energy Review” by the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL, 2022) assumes a mean discount rate of 6.57% for onshore wind turbines. For NPVs with varied discount rates

Fig. 4. The impact functions (or power curves) of the wind turbine types used to determine at what fraction of its total capacity the corresponding wind turbine can produce energy at given wind-speeds.

Table 2

Expected yearly energy production and wind damage for conventional turbines (left) and typhoon-resistant (right) wind turbines. ‘Baseline’ climate uses a probabilistic tropical cyclone (TC) event set representing climate conditions in 1980–2017, while ‘future’ climate uses a TC set for 2015–2050 under SSP585; GWA indicates Global Wind Atlas values for non-TC conditions (see Methods Section 3.1).

	Climate Scenario	Conventional turbines	Typhoon-resistant turbines
Energy production [GW/a] in normal wind conditions	GWA	10,847	24,435
Energy production [GW/a] typhoons	Baseline	11.6	29.4
	Future	13.6	34.8
Damages [Mio. US\$/a] due to typhoons	Baseline	1.2	0.009
	Future	3.7	0.04

consult Table 4 in the Appendix B. The full cost–benefit analysis was done twice, once considering typhoons as in current climate conditions (2020), and in the climate of 2050 given the warming scenario RCP8.5 (business as usual, compatible with worldwide climate policies in 2020 (Schwalm et al., 2020)).

3.2. Results

3.2.1. Strengths

First steps towards a more renewable-oriented energy transition are already evident, such as the start of the commercial operation of the country’s first large-scale offshore wind farm (Lee, 2022). In addition, the cooperation of several market leaders and start-ups, whose successes are partly based on strong research and technological readiness, enables continuous adaptation and innovation in the wind energy sector (Challenergy Inc., 2020; Vestas, 2020; Gamesa, 2021). In the course of this development and the knowledge of typhoon occurrence, more typhoon-resistant wind turbines have been procured in recent years. The paper’s quantitative analysis models that status-quo wind turbine types and typhoon-resistant turbines produce 10 847 GWh and 24 435 GWh energy per year during normal wind conditions (see Table 2). The average annual production from typhoons in the current climate is considerably smaller with 11.6 and 25.5 GWh. This amounts to a yearly benefit of US\$ 2.3 billion for status-quo and US\$ 5.1 billion for typhoon-resistant wind turbines at market prices (Fig. 6).

In contrast, typhoons cause average annual damages of roughly US\$ 1.3 million to the status-quo turbines and around US\$ 9 thousand to the typhoon-resistant turbine types in the current climate (Fig. 6). This damage from typhoons adds up to 0.02% of the total investment value of all status-quo wind turbines and to minimal damages to the typhoon-resistant turbines. Additional to the damages from typhoons, the costs comprise of fix costs (wind turbine construction: US\$1.3 million/MWh capacity) and running costs (such as operation & maintenance: US\$14.3/MWh produced). The total costs amount to US\$405 million per year for the status-quo and US\$909 million for the typhoon-resistant wind turbines.

Put together, in the existing climate, there is a yearly net benefit of roughly US\$1.9 billion for the status-quo and US\$4.2 billion for the typhoon-resistant wind turbines. Over their assumed 20-year lifetime this amounts to a net benefit of US\$21.7 billion for status-quo and US\$49 billion for typhoon-resistant turbines with a discount rate of 5% (Fig. 6). As seen in Table 3, the numbers stay relatively similar when considering changes in damages and energy production due to climate change. There is still a net profit of US\$21.7 billion for status-quo and US\$49 billion for typhoon-resistant turbines. The high profitability is expressed by BCR of 4.25 for the status-quo and 4.26 for the typhoon-resistant wind turbines in the existing climate, which makes the typhoon-resistant wind turbines slightly more profitable.

Fig. 5. SWOT analysis of the Japanese wind energy sector under the influence of typhoons and climate change. The analysis is divided into the four SWOT components and illustrates the methods and subject areas of each section.

Fig. 6. Benefits and costs for status-quo and typhoon-resistant wind turbine types with and without climate change.

3.2.2. Weaknesses

An important weakness of the energy sector is that conventional wind turbines have limited resistance to strong winds and either fail to produce electricity or, in the worst case, may even be damaged (Challenergy Inc., 2020; Gamesa, 2021). Indeed, as our analysis with CLIMADA has shown, typhoons cause considerable damage to Japanese wind turbines. For status-quo turbines, the total damage amounts to US\$1.2 million per year (0.3% of total costs, including investment, fixed and damage costs) without climate change and US\$3.7 million per year (0.9% of total costs) with climate change (see Table 2). Appendix B shows additional information on how the damages were calculated and how the parameters used from Rose et al. (2013) influence the damages to wind turbines.

Another big remaining challenge of a system consisting of 100% renewable energy is ensuring that the demand for electricity can always be reliably met (Esteban and Portugal-Pereira, 2014). Despite the possibility of battery energy storage through, for example,

Table 3

Cost–benefit analysis for conventional (left) and typhoon-resistant (right) wind turbines. ‘Baseline’ climate uses a probabilistic tropical cyclone (TC) event set representing climate conditions in 1980–2017, while ‘future’ climate uses a TC set for 2015–2050 under SSP585 (see Methods Section 3.1).

	Climate Scenario	Conventional turbines	Typhoon-resistant turbines
Total Benefits [Mio. US\$/a]	<i>Baseline</i>	2.28	5.14
	<i>Future</i>	2.28	5.14
Total Costs [Mio. US\$/a]	<i>Baseline</i>	0.40	0.91
	<i>Future</i>	0.41	0.91
Net-Benefit [Mio. US\$/a]	<i>Baseline</i>	1.88	4.23
	<i>Future</i>	1.87	4.23
NPV over lifetime (5% discount rate) [Mio. US\$]	<i>Baseline</i>	21.73	49.01
	<i>Future</i>	21.71	49.02
Benefit-cost-ratio (5% discount rate)	<i>Baseline</i>	4.25	4.26
	<i>Future</i>	4.23	4.26

lithium and flow batteries, one of our experts highlights that removing fossil fuels fully from the electricity grid is going to be challenging (Chokani, 2022).

3.2.3. Opportunities

The implementation of the feed-in tariff system (FiT) in 2011 enabled Japan to subsidize the construction of renewable energy power plants (Fraser, 2020). In addition, financial support allocated by the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI) for energy policy has enabled a significant deployment of renewable energies (Suenaga et al., 2020). Among these, onshore and offshore wind energy has a greater installation potential (Mizuno, 2014). The switch to alternative energy sources (IEA, 2018) is also attractive regarding Japan’s import-dependency for almost all energy resources since the dependency creates challenges if an energy supply problem were to occur abroad.

In addition to energy security, this shift offers significant economic opportunities, particularly through fostering localized industrial growth. Remote islands such as Tsushima, which have vast potential for renewable energy expansion, stand to benefit greatly. However, the key to maximizing these benefits lies in developing local industries capable of producing and maintaining renewable energy infrastructure, thereby reducing economic leakages to external markets. This would create jobs, enhance technical expertise, and promote self-sufficiency, leading to long-term sustainability (Matsumoto and Matsumura, 2022; EIB, 2022; Swiss Re, 2024).

Furthermore, since 42% of total carbon emissions of the country stem from the electricity sector (Cheng et al., 2022), a shift to renewable energy sources offers an opportunity to significantly reduce emissions. Such a shift would align with the government’s goal of reaching a carbon neutral society (Cheng et al., 2022; Matsumoto and Matsumura, 2022).

The existing nuclear power plant grid infrastructure on the coasts of Japan can also be used for the distribution of electricity from wind turbines (Suenaga et al., 2020). This offers opportunities for the country’s infrastructure sector by reducing the need for new grid construction and utilizing the current network to integrate wind energy with minimal investment (Komiya and Fujii, 2021). In contrast to the common assumption, wind turbines do not lead to grid instability. Nevertheless, this requires upgrades to the grid (Chokani, 2022). Since electric grid infrastructure also faces risks due to climate change, studies such as Brockway and Dunn (2020) show how to make informed long-term planning decisions. According to Chokani (2022), a successful transformation to renewable energies also requires planning the utilization of the generated energy which varies over time. However, this is made possible through forecasts nowadays, providing a prognosis of variations in wind and solar conditions. This facilitates the decision as to when to store or use the generated energy to ensure the most even supply possible (Chokani, 2022). Considering the consequence of the Fukushima disaster, it can also be assumed that a shift to renewable energy sources can make energy generation less dangerous (Esteban and Portugal-Pereira, 2014).

Finally, since the 1990s the liberalization of the Japanese electricity market has progressed, which was previously dominated by ten regionally integrated companies with a quasi-monopoly in their respective areas. After a gradual opening of the competition, the market was fully liberalized in 2016 (Dupuis, 2021), which may be favorable also for international companies focusing on new renewable energy production means such as wind turbines. This liberalization, alongside Japan’s increasing trade openness, presents significant opportunities for foreign firms entering the renewable energy sector.

As identified in Section 3.2.2, a weakness of current wind turbines is the damage caused by typhoons. An opportunity presents itself through the wind turbine manufacturers who have already been working on improving the resistance of conventional wind turbines under typhoon conditions (Rechsteiner, 2023). The analysis has shown that typhoon-resistant turbines have a significantly higher energy production while also having significantly lower damages, yielding thus higher total benefit (see Table 2, 3 and Fig. 6). The total and especially investment costs are higher for typhoon-resistant turbines but this is compensated by a high benefit. Consequently, typhoon-resistant turbines have a significantly higher NPV and a higher BCR. They outperform status-quo wind turbines when considering climate change. Even with climate change the cost caused by typhoon damage is below 0.001% of the total cost (comprised of fix, running and damage costs) for typhoon-resistant turbines. For conventional turbines damage costs are 0.3% of total cost without and 0.9% with climate change.

The analysis with CLIMADA indicates that climate change could also be an opportunity for the production of wind energy during typhoons. When considering climate change models, there is an increase in energy production during typhoons with a slightly higher

increase for the typhoon-resistant turbine type. The median across all climate change models predicts an increase in annual typhoon energy production of 17% for the status-quo and 18% for the typhoon-resistant turbine type.

However, the amount of energy produced during typhoons represents only 0.001% of the total energy produced during normal wind conditions throughout the rest of the year. This observation is reinforced by [Rechsteiner \(2023\)](#), according to whom typhoons are not in themselves a suitable source of energy because their short phases only lead to very poor utilization of a turbine designed to produce energy during typhoons. The benefits from typhoon-resistant turbines come mainly from the damage reduction.

3.2.4. Threats

Despite the FiT system and subsidies, the development and expansion of wind power in Japan have been slow. In 2019, 76% of the energy produced originated from fossil fuels and 6% from nuclear energy. In 2020, the wind energy sector contributed about 18% of the total energy mix ([Suenaga et al., 2020](#)). The electricity market, limited network capacity, and the grid operation practices of electricity suppliers have slowed down the increase in the installation of wind turbines ([Mizuno, 2014](#)). Due to Japan's limited experience in the wind industry, its growth is dependent on the pace of construction of FiT projects and any offshore project proposals ([Abdelilah et al., 2020](#)). On the political level, the challenges are mainly related to the fact that the country is characterized by a certain sectionalism, which has a weakening effect on the development of the energy transition, as it contributes to competition between ministries and thus makes cooperation more difficult ([Suenaga et al., 2020](#)). In addition, Japan has strict bans on the installation of photovoltaic or onshore wind turbines primarily in residential and protected forest areas. It is also considerate of ensuring its food self-sufficiency by preventing the conversion of farmland ([Obane et al., 2020](#)). The liberalization of the energy market enables the population and businesses to choose electric power suppliers largely by themselves. Nevertheless, because of the still existing oligopolistic structures with very few providers and due to grid access restrictions for new suppliers, sources contradict each other on whether this liberalization has fully taken place and thus already contributes to the renewable energy transition ([Rechsteiner, 2023](#)).

Altogether, the situation for renewable energy seems to be more challenging than in other countries ([Chokani, 2022](#)). Whilst the Asian-Pacific region counted 394 GW of wind power in 2021, it is expected to host nearly 693 GW by the end of 2028. Among this, China will account for 567GW, 93% of which will be onshore, whilst India's total capacity will reach 60GW. In contrast, Japan's total capacity will reach 6.4GW onshore and 4GW offshore by the end of 2028 ([Carr and Wang, 2022](#)).

Major uncertainties will also arrive for the economic, political, and social sectors. The current trend of hydrogen-derived ammonia shows that other innovations cannot compete with current renewable energy sources so far in terms of price, sustainability, and efficiency ([Parkes, 2022](#)). Nevertheless, this leads to speculations on whether future innovations could compete with the current ways of energy production, e.g. having a more stable infrastructure than many renewable energy installations. Japan's strong lobby for existing power-generating technologies such as nuclear power will hinder the willingness to invest in the path towards the integration of wind energy ([Chokani, 2022](#)). Additionally, the success of development in the energy sector will depend on uncertainties in demographic developments, such as Japan's declining population and aging society. This, among other things, could entail a change or decrease in energy demand ([IEA, 2018](#)).

Lastly, climate change can also be viewed as a threat since the model predicts that damages are three to five times higher in the future period than in the reference period (see [Table 2](#)). Even though the damages are higher and the total benefits stay similar, the discounted BCR for the status-quo turbines decreases only slightly from 4.25 to 4.23 considering climate change, and for the typhoon-resistant turbines remains the same at 4.26. This is due to the damages from the typhoons representing only a small fraction compared to the large benefits from the energy production. However, owing to changes in typhoon characteristics caused by advancing climate change, the Japanese power system will continue to experience some unpredictable adverse effects ([Ciais et al., 2013](#); [Mori et al., 2021](#)).

3.3. Discussion

The findings of this study suggest that wind energy investment in Japan holds significant economic potential. Even though Japan faces yearly strong typhoons, the analysis has shown that the benefits outweigh the costs for both status-quo and typhoon-resistant wind turbines. It can be seen that the typhoon-resistant wind turbines outperform the status-quo turbines with regard to energy production, total benefit, and BCR. In addition, they experience significantly less damage from typhoons. The main reason for the higher benefits of the typhoon-resistant turbine is however the higher capacity, which leads to more energy production (4.1 MW compared to 1.82 MW for a status-quo turbine).

The results of our model show several policy implications for businesses. These include that climate change will increase damage to wind energy infrastructure and that the additional wind energy production during typhoons is not very significant. Nevertheless, the analysis demonstrates that wind energy remains a profitable venture even under changing climatic conditions for both turbine types, and despite the unfavorable conditions of the Japanese energy sector. This resilience underscores the long-term viability of wind energy as a sustainable power source in Japan. While the analysis primarily focuses on onshore wind turbines, it is important to acknowledge the potential of offshore wind energy in Japan. Offshore turbines typically exhibit higher capacity and could therefore offer even greater opportunities for wind energy generation ([IRENA, 2022](#)). Should this option be considered, factors such as deep sea level drop ([Komiya and Fujii, 2021](#)) and piracy must be considered and further research conducted ([Chokani, 2022](#)). Overall, the study emphasizes the need to develop typhoon-resistant wind turbines. By enhancing the sector's resilience, wind energy can continue to thrive and contribute to Japan's renewable energy goals.

However, the restrictive market dynamics in Japan, compounded by influential players such as the energy suppliers that hinder the transition to renewables, pose considerable challenges. As observed in the expert interviews, these barriers may impede the widespread deployment of wind energy in the future. Furthermore, the transition to renewables faces substantial challenges arising from entrenched political and social structures. Despite liberalization efforts, the current measures have not been sufficient to drive substantial renewable energy adoption. To facilitate a smooth and effective transition, it is therefore imperative to address these market-related, social, and political barriers by enacting supportive policies. This would create a level playing field for fair grid access including unbundling operators of production and transmission and an independent market surveillance, encouraging stakeholder collaboration, and raising awareness among the public. It is crucial to address these constraints, fostering a more favorable environment for renewable energy investment and exploiting its full potential (Rechsteiner, 2023).

There are certain limitations to this illustrative case study that future research can address. Relying solely on open-source data and literature - with limited access to local experts' perspectives and important considerations - potentially affects the accuracy of the analysis or shows an incomplete picture. Only publicly available literature in the English and German language was accessed, which likely poses a limit to the understanding of the socio-political environment. On the quantitative side, there are several limitations stemming from the input data: the investment and running costs, as well as the impact functions modeling the power curves of the turbines and the damages due to typhoons, are estimates based on available public data. The location and number of wind turbines are limited to those listed in OpenStreetMap which is likely to be incomplete (Biljecki et al., 2023). Furthermore, the normal wind conditions as well as the number and location of wind turbines were assumed to stay the same with climate change, disregarding potential changes. Also, this paper considered the situation when all turbines are either status-quo or typhoon-resistant turbines, which is a clear simplification. The used STORM hazard dataset does not describe the extra-tropical transition and is thus likely to overestimate the typhoon wind intensity in Japan (Bloemendaal et al., 2020, 2022). Finally, although the analysis shows the potential of an investment in typhoon-resistant wind turbines, the question remains how Japan can implement these changes and become more sustainable with constrained investment or public expenditure. This could be addressed in a future study by including methods that consider different budget constraints and comparing several adaptation strategies.

Nevertheless, the close alignment between this study's results and findings from other seminal literature validates the reliability and accuracy of the calculations. This report estimates an annual electricity production from status-quo wind turbines of 10.9 TWh. The fact that the estimate matches the data of IEA (2021b), which claims the annual wind energy production of 2021 in Japan to be 8.47 TWh, provides further confidence in the robustness of this paper's methodology and enhances the credibility of the analysis. Furthermore, the integration of quantitative risk assessment with qualitative research, embedded within a SWOT analysis, has proven valuable in providing a holistic understanding of the wind energy sector in Japan. In general, the framework presented can be applied in more detail and more abstractly depending on the diversity of resources and quality of data acquired. The informative value and relevance of the results of an analysis using the methods presented therefore depend on the inputs. In conclusion, this case study highlights the potential and challenges associated with wind energy deployment in Japan. By addressing the economic, socio-political, and climate-related considerations, policymakers and industry stakeholders can foster an enabling environment for renewable energy investments.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, a SWOT methodology is proposed to analyze the potential of economic sectors and businesses in the face of a changing climate. The method allows for the direct integration of quantitative risk assessment with qualitative research in a framework suitable for guiding business and investment decisions. This presents a substantially more complete and holistic picture when compared to the frequently performed cost-benefit analysis alone. Furthermore, compared to pure adaptation option appraisal approaches, the presented SWOT application allows to shift the discourse from avoidance of negative outcomes to strategic planning in an evolving environment.

The paper demonstrates the application of the potential of the wind energy sector in Japan considering climate risks associated with typhoons. It shows that even based solely on openly available data it is possible to quantitatively analyze the risk as well as examine the socio-economic context. There are many promising future directions that could build upon and extend the current methodology to address the complexities of climate change by including different dimensions of risks and opportunities. For instance, one may expand the quantitative methodology that can be applied in a multi-hazard setting (Stalhandske et al., 2023), or consider the multi-facets of exposed elements (Mühlhofer et al., 2024). The qualitative analysis could be complemented with a stakeholder or institutional analysis (Farrokhnia M. and A., 2023; Namugenyi et al., 2019; Benzaghta et al., 2021).

Overall, this article can serve as a blueprint for future studies in this field, enabling researchers and industry stakeholders to analyze the feasibility and challenges of technological transitions in the context of changing climate risks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lisa Bachmann: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ricarda Lex:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Florian Regli:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Saira Vögeli:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Evelyn Mühlhofer:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jamie W. McCaughey:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Susanne Hanger-Kopp:** Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David N. Bresch:** Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Chahan M. Kropf:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT and DeepL in order to improve language and readability in few parts of this paper. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Chahan M. Kropf reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Jamie McCaughey reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Evelyn Muehlhofer reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Discount rates

See [Table 4](#).

Table 4

Net-Present-Value (NPV) of conventional and typhoon-resistant wind turbines for different discount rates assuming a wind turbine lifetime of 20 years. 'Baseline' climate uses a probabilistic tropical cyclone (TC) event set representing climate conditions in 1980–2017, while 'future' climate uses a TC set for 2015–2050 under SSP585 (see Methods Section 3.1).

Discount rate	Climate Scenario	NPV of Conventional turbines [Mio. US\$]	NPV of Typhoon-resistant turbines [Mio. US\$]
5% ^a	Baseline	21.73	49.01
	Future	21.71	49.02
0%	Baseline	37.51	84.57
	Future	37.47	84.59
2.5%	Baseline	28.26	63.72
	Future	28.23	63.74
7.5%	Baseline	17.03	38.40
	Future	17.01	38.41

^a A discount rate of 5% was used throughout the paper as a baseline.

Appendix B. Damage

In this section we describe how we used Eq. (3) and the parameters α and β from [Rose et al. \(2013\)](#) to create our sigmoid shaped damage impact function (see [Fig. 3](#)). [Table 5](#) shows the mean values used for these parameters and their standard deviation (SD). The annual resulting damages to conventional wind turbines based on the mean parameters α and β are displayed in [Table 6](#), while [Table 7](#) shows how the damages to the wind turbines change based on the variation of α and β by +/- 2 standard deviations. Changes in α and β had no impact on the typhoon-resistant turbines in our model and thus these damages are not shown in the aforementioned tables.

$$\log - \text{logistic}(v; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{v/\alpha^\beta}{1 + v/\alpha^\beta} \quad (3)$$

Table 5

Breakdown of the parameters α and β and their standard deviation used in the impact damage functions (see Eq. (3)) based on data from [Rose et al. \(2013\)](#).

	Mean	Std. Dev.
α	139.6	0.455
β	18.6	0.998

Table 6

Breakdown of the damages to conventional wind turbines in US\$ per year using the mean α and β described in Table 5. 'Baseline' climate scenario uses a probabilistic tropical cyclone (TC) event set representing climate conditions in 1980–2017, while 'future' climate uses a TC set for 2015–2050 under SSP585 (see Methods Section 3.1). Both of these scenarios also include damages that result from normal winds, that were calculated using a single annual average wind map of Japan (100 m above sea level).

Climate Scenario	Damages to conventional wind turbines [US\$/a]
Baseline	\$ 1'336'196
Future	\$ 3'828'494

Table 7

Breakdown of the variation of the damages in US\$ per year for conventional wind turbines (1.82 MW) when varying the parameters alpha and beta by +/-2 standard deviations (SD). Table 6 shows the damage values to the wind turbines when the mean values for α and β are used. 'Baseline' climate scenario uses a probabilistic tropical cyclone (TC) event set representing climate conditions in 1980–2017, while 'future' climate uses a TC set for 2015–2050 under SSP585 (see Methods Section 3.1). Both of these scenarios also include damages that result from normal winds, that were calculated using a single annual average wind map of Japan (100 m above sea level).

Parameter Variation	Scenario	Damages (+2 SD) [US\$/a]	Damages (-2 SD) [US\$/a]
Keeping β constant and varying α	Baseline	\$ 1'187'907	\$ 1'503'711
	Future	\$ 3'417'760	\$ 4'289'192
Keeping α constant and varying β	Baseline	\$ 703'708	\$ 2'922'591
	Future	\$ 2'471'925	\$ 6'646'980
Varying both α and β	Baseline	\$ 618'419	\$ 3'250'529
	Future	\$ 2'182'829	\$ 7'366'712

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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